

premetaphase chromosomes of males, the relative length of autosomes ranged from 0.022 to 0.047. The NOR measured 0.047; the X-chromosome, 0.022; and the Y, 0.016 (Fig. 2A). The relative length of autosomes in females ranged from 0.013 to 0.045. The relative length of NOR was 0.029, that of the X-chromosome was 0.043 (Fig. 2B).

Very few cells (3/individual) were detected undergoing anaphase immediately after metaphase. Anaphase occurred so fast that it was least trapped in fixed brain tissue. In contrast, the frequency of telophase cells was high (30 cells/individual). Later, cytokinesis ensued and formed two daughter nuclei. The first prophase nucleus measured 7.05μ by 5.88μ . Each nucleus had a circular nucleolus 1.76μ in diameter. Seven more variations of prophase nuclei were found (see table).

During the regular mitotic cycle in *N. lugens* biotype 1, prophase was the

Prophase forms of brain cells of *N. lugens* biotype 1.

Prophase form	Length (μ)	Width (μ)	Remarks
II	8.23	7.64	Nuclear membrane present; nucleolus present; chromosomes granulated
III	11.17	10.58	Nuclear membrane and nucleolus disintegrating; chromosomes granulated
IV	15.29	13.52	Nuclear membrane disappearing; nucleolus absent; chromosomes appeared as intertwined threads
V	17.64	14.11	Same as above
VI	11.76	7.06	Nuclear membrane disappeared; chromosomes elongated
VII	8.23	7.06	Chromosomes condensed into irregular forms and scattered all over the nucleus
VIII	17.64	10.58	Irregular scattered chromosomes

longest stage, followed by telophase and metaphase; anaphase was the shortest.

Some brain cell nuclei displayed either an increase (agmatoploidy) or decrease (hypoploidy) in chromosome numbers. Hypoploidy resulted from somatic chromosomal fusions (Fig. 1f).

Agmatoploidy resulted from chromosomal fragmentations, leading to the appearance of extra chromosomes, such as m-chromosomes. On the whole, hypoploidy was more frequent than agmatoploidy in *N. lugens* biotype 1. *S*

Parasitoids of the rice gall midge (GM) in Indonesia

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Several hymenopterous parasitoids of GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) have been recorded in Java and Bali (see figure):

Egg-larval parasitoid:

Platygaster oryzae Cameron
(Platygasteridae)

Larval parasitoids:

Propicroscytus mirificus (Girault)
(Pteromalidae)

Eurytoma setitibia Gahan
(Eurytomidae)

Trichorhina sp. (Diapriidae)

Tetrastichus sp. *nyemitawus* Rohwe
groups (Eulophidae)

Pupal parasitoid:

Neanastatus oryzae Ferriere
(Eupelmidae)

Only *P. oryzae*, *N. oryzae*, and *P. mirificus* are considered important. In surveys during 3 consecutive years, *P.*

Distribution of *P. oryzae* and *N. oryzae* in Java, Indonesia.

oryzae and *N. oryzae* were normally found; *P. mirificus* was found only with intensive observation. *P. oryzae* was found in 91% and *N. oryzae* in 70% of the locations where silvershoots were

sampled. The degree of parasitization varied, but ranged from 30 to 70%. Based on the number of parasitized hosts, the ratio of *P. oryzae* to *N. oryzae* ranged from 3.3:1 to 6.8:1. *S*